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“Sec Buzzers”

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Abstract

Cybersecurity and confronting cyber threats is a dynamic process in that advances in technology are continually evolving, and the cybersecurity enterprise, both the private sector and the public sector must confront these threats generally after vulnerabilities are exposed. This dynamic presents a very challenging practice in that the wide array of persons, networks, and organizations with malicious intentions do have the strategic advantages in that completed security controls for the new technological advances are not analogous to the new innovations or the new vulnerabilities that are created. Therefore, any emerging cyber security technology is usually the result of recently discovered vulnerabilities and not proactive cybersecurity initiatives. Sec Buzzers represents an emergent method and additional tool for organizations to share and identify updated vulnerabilities and threats in a semi-transparent environment.

Introduction

Cybersecurity and confronting cyber threats is a dynamic process in that advances in technology are continually evolving, and the cybersecurity enterprise, both the private sector and the public sector must confront these threats generally after vulnerabilities are exposed. This dynamic presents a very challenging practice in that the wide array of persons, networks, and organizations with malicious intentions do have the strategic advantages in that completed security controls for the new technological advances are not analogous to the new innovations or the new vulnerabilities that are created. Therefore, any emerging cyber security technology is usually the result of recently discovered vulnerabilities and not proactive cybersecurity initiatives.

A recent example of this dynamic in cybersecurity is wireless technology. Wireless technology expanded as a preferred technology given the ease of establishing a network infrastructure and an increase in mobility of devices and services (Carmen, & Diana-Elena, 2012). The speed and dependence on wireless networks are only intensifying as more and more devices are connecting wirelessly (King & Evans, 2016), the use of Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) policies (Bello Garba, Armarego & Murray 2015) and the cloud environment as an emergent data storage warehouse. As commercial networks such as Long Term Evolution (LTE) enters the fifth generation (5G), security standards continue to develop (Chin, Fan & Haines, 2014). Security standards are continually attempting to catch up to the most recent technology. The most recent history of the evolution, use, and advancement of wireless technology over the last several decades is a microcosm of the imbalance between advanced technology and standardized security protocols in cybersecurity.

Emerging Cybersecurity Technologies – Sec Buzzers

Sec Buzzers is an emerging cybersecurity framework and strategy that endeavors to protect social media applications as a web based service (Hsieh, Lee, Mao, Lai, Kao & Dai, 2015). Social media and network applications have unique cybersecurity issues and Sec Buzzers cybersecurity application accelerates implementation of cybersecurity protections (Hsieh, Lee, Mao, Lai, Kao & Dai, 2015). A major cybersecurity threat is the sheer enormity of the number of persons using social media platforms (Reddy & Reddy, 2014). This is increasing the opportunities for cyber-crime criminals given that social media provides platforms for transmitting personal information and social engineering vulnerabilities. For example, many social media networks such as Instagram and Facebook offer location applications in that the individual user transmits the specific location they are at. This provides a unique vulnerability in social media.

Social media platforms provide also provide another unique challenge to organizations in confronting cybercrime in that organizations have very limited control over employees that use social media (Reddy & Reddy, 2014). Given the traditional challenges of insiders involved in cyber-crime, this presents another opportunity for the misuse of an organizational information technology. Social media applications are more akin to social interactions than an operational framework used for work-related purposes in an organizational setting (Pipyros, Mitrou, Gritzalis & Apostolopoulos,

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2014). For example, it is relatively easy (when compared to social media) to implement technical or administrative controls on an organization's network when compared to trying to regulate the use of social media by an employee. The vulnerabilities and risks inherent to social media platforms represent an evolution of the new professional workforce that melds social networking and traditional work roles. According to Pipyros, Mitrou, Gritzalis & Apostolopoulos (2014), social media is defined by social interactions and therefore, this domain is increasingly hard to regulate given the informal nature of the communication and lack of governing (and enforceable) rules in most social media platforms. Social media vulnerabilities also provide yet another risk and vulnerability in that a significant amount of business intelligence and analytics (BI&A) is conducted through social media platforms (Chen, Chiang & Storey, 2012). Even legitimate businesses are drawn to social media given the potential. Social media provide a rich environment for data mining and analytics given the relatively free flow of information in very unguarded networks and applications. Essentially, this is tantamount to intrusions and data mining from many different sources and origins further complicating the cybersecurity landscape. Emerging cybersecurity technologies should have the ability to disentangle the data from social media and leverage the potential benefits from that data.

Sec Buzzers

Sec Buzzers is an emerging ambitious information cyber security technology that seeks to both discover new threats and offer a remedy for the solutions (Hsieh, Lee, Mao, Lai, Kao & Dai, 2015). Sec Buzzers is a web based technology that differs from previous technologies in that Sec Buzzers endeavors to proactively determine cybersecurity threats. More specifically, Sec Buzzers is an online community that searches for topics highlighting vulnerabilities through Twitter, a popular social media outlet. The current network expanse of Twitter is staggering. According to the corporation website, there are 320 million active users and approximately one billion unique visits monthly (Twitter, 2016, para. 2). On a typical day, there are approximately 278 thousand tweets every sixty (6) seconds (Gritzalis, 2014). Additionally, Twitter supports over thirty five languages (Twitter, 2016, para 2). The enormity of this social media outlet network, both quantitatively (number of users) and qualitative (languages and variations of content) and speed and intensity of the flow of information provides significant opportunities for legitimate and non-legitimate purposes.

Sec Buzzers is based on the concept of Open Source Intelligence (OSINT) (Gritzalis, 2014). Essentially, sharing information from public sources. Although not all the cybersecurity information gleaned from the Twitter network is publicly available, a core component of Sec Buzzers (similar to OSINT) is sharing. More specifically, sharing and disseminative in a very timely manner according to the OSINT model (Gritzalis, 2014). The more (and faster) the sharing, the larger the growth of the expert community to cultivate more cybersecurity strategies and technologies. At the core of Sec Buzzers is to speed the dissemination of a cybersecurity vulnerability or risk. This is generally counter to the first few generations of vulnerabilities, particularly zero day exploits (ZDE) (Bilge & Dumitras, 2012) in that organizations were reluctant to release and publicize discovered ZDE's for a variety of reason. However, the open domain and platform models, and uses of social media require a new technological model to both discover and reveal vulnerabilities. Sec Buzzers is designed to address these two shortcomings in cybersecurity: an open community discovering a vulnerability and the speed in disseminating that vulnerability to address a remedy.

The core foci of Sec Buzzers consists of three components: efficient and scalable social media connector, weighting community-related Twitter users and uncovering emerging topics

(Hsieh, Lee, Mao, Lai, Kao & Dai, 2015, p. 28). The first component is the social media connector. The social media connector matches social media tweets based on the content of the

Tweets and then formulates a specific thread based upon a topic related to a cybersecurity threat.

The second component of the framework is to pool the community of Twitter cybersecurity experts. These community of experts in the online community will then rank and scale the threat using connectors. This pool of cybersecurity experts will then be weighted. The third component of Sec Buzzers is to form an algorithm that is the best remedy for a cyber security vulnerability. Ideally, a database will be created from this framework that could potentially serve has a help forum of all contemporary vulnerabilities. Sec Buzzers is designed to have the type cybersecurity experts discussed a recently discovered vulnerability and share a remedy for that vulnerability (Hsieh, Lee, Mao, Lai, Kao, & Dai, 2015).

Examples of Sec Buzzers

Sec Buzzers recently applied the framework from two recent attacks, "Venom" and "Duqu 2.0". Venom was a moniker given to an attack of the "virtualized environment neglected operations manipulation" (Hsieh, Lee, Mao, Lai, Kao, & Dai,

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2015, p. 30) that was discovered on May 31, 2015. The Venom malware attacked floppy drives of virtual machines (InfoSec Institute, 2016). The Venom malware vulnerability possible dates back to 2004 and is stored in the QEMU Database and increases a significant amount of data centers to this vulnerability (InfoSec Institute, 2016). Venom malware has the potential to allow the attacker to break out of the guest Virtual Machine (Win, Tianfield & Mair, 2015). The social media connectors identified the topics related to the Venom database and begin to search the topic. Within five (5) days, the online community was able to discover that Oracle had discovered a patch to the Venom malware (Hsieh, Lee, Mao, Lai, Kao & Dai, 2015). One of the shortcomings of this example is that it is impossible to know how long this patch would take to discover if the Sec Buzzers online community and connectors did not exist. The second example and impact of Sec Buzzers is the Duqu 2.0 malware. The Duqu 2.0 can be considered “the most sophisticated malware ever” developed (Hsieh, Lee, Mao, Lai, Kao, & Dai, 2015, p. 30). Duqu 2.0 was discovered in 2004 and classified as an Advanced Persistent Threat (APT). The Sec Buzzer analyzed two peaks of topic identification in the middle of June 2015 consisting of over 300,000 tweets related to the Duqu 2.0 vulnerability (Hsieh, Lee, Mao, Lai, Kao, & Dai, 2015). From these connectors, over one hundred (100) security experts were identified by connectors within the 300,000 tweets. Further analysis of these experts identified three (3) clusters, one of which had the most impact on finding a solution for the Duqu 2.0 vulnerability. Overall, the authors predict that clusters of cybersecurity experts can be predicted in 85% of the threads (Hsieh, Lee, Mao, Lai, Kao, & Dai, 2015) making Sec Buzzers are very viable social networking data mining technology.

Organizational Uses of Sec Buzzers

The emerging tool of Sec Buzzers is several significant uses for an organization. The major contribution of Sec Buzzers is within the framework of Open Source Intelligence (OPSINT) and data mining techniques. Sec Buzzers significantly increases the sophistication of

OPSINT and improves the OPSINT model to a more focused data mining tool that organizations can use for reactive and proactive protection of networks. The basic, contemporary OPSINT model uses data from social networks and social media to predict anomalies and respond to those

anomalies (Gritzalis, 2014). Sec Buzzers provides a framework in that organizations can link predictive threats with a potential solution.

Sec Buzzers can also be used by organizations to determine quality cybersecurity experts and potentially hire them as consultants. Hiring and retaining quality cybersecurity professionals is challenging given the lack of standards and education necessary in the field of cybersecurity. As cybersecurity continues to evolve and develop, the job has become increasingly complex (Martini & Choo, 2014). The next generation of cybersecurity experts, like all professions, will be required to be more educated and able to engage in multiple cybersecurity tasks, including analyzing newer and more resilient malware.

Sec Buzzers can be used by organizations to identify and top cybersecurity experts by a performance-based system. For example, cyber security experts can be ranked based on their performance on Sec Buzzers in identifying vulnerabilities and speed in disseminating a resolution. Ideally, the top cybersecurity experts receive the greatest rewards. In essence, Sec Buzzers can create a driven market system in that the best cybersecurity experts are compensated at the highest rates, creating a free market system and encouraging speed and intensity in identifying devastating malware. A performance based system based on the best cybersecurity experts identifying the vulnerabilities and providing solutions in a timely manner. Given the current system, most organizations are not concerned with a malware attack unless the organization’s network or applications are effected. The current system of cybersecurity is provincial and reactive based. Sec Buzzers has the potential to create an open, capitalist system of proactive cybersecurity experts. Sec Buzzers may also have the benefit of improving the overall profession if this model continues to evolve.

Role of the Federal Government and Sec Buzzers

The role of the government in creating data mining tools similar to Sec Buzzers is very complex. The Federal Government should continue to cultivate data mining and community building tools such as Sec Buzzers given that that Federal Government. Federal Government involvement in this technology will engage the “public safety versus individual rights” debate (Dubber, 2014). This is an enduring paradigm in democracies such as the United States that involve monitoring and warehousing of information gleaned from the public. This balancing framework is based on

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ideological ebbs and tides (i.e., Liberal versus Conservative sentiment) and how threatening a malware attack is to the public. Generally, the public may be more malleable and tolerant of government intervention on malware attacks on national defense systems. It is unclear how the public may view Federal Government intervention in malware attacks that center on private sector networks. Essentially, there is a mistrust of the Federal Government involving any form of information that originates from the public and creating an alliance with the private sector.

The most recent and analogous issue involving the Federal Government in a data mining technology partnership is the current case of Apple's CEO refusing a court order to allow a federal law enforcement agency (the Federal Bureau of Investigation {FBI}) to compel Apple to engage in a data mining algorithm to retrieve data from an iPhone (Wingfield & Issac, 2016). The case involved two couples that were involved in a mass shooting in San Bernadino, CA in December 2015 in which fourteen (14) persons and twenty-two (22) injured (Wingfield & Issac, 2016). The couple's iPhone was destroyed, and the FBI requested that Apple provide the data from the iPhone that was potentially stored on Apple's server. The FBI As of this writing, Tim Cook has refused the order of a Federal judge to provide the data. This recent issue highlights the trepidation has regarding entering a partnership with the federal government regarding the sharing of data unless there is a specific business necessity. This pervasive relationship is historically rooted in the Fourth Amendment and the relationship between citizens and the federal government. Private sector organizations such consider themselves as private citizens in this relationship or at least do not want to be a conduit for the government to circumvent these rights.

Benefits

There are several benefits for the Federal government for embracing and cultivating a data mining technology such as Sec Buzzers. One of the initial benefits is the deterrent effect this technology may have on malicious hackers. Federal government participation in this technology may advertise to the malicious hacking community that the government has access to tools and expertise to confront potential attacks. At this moment, there is a very little deterrent effect on potential hackers. Additionally, another potential benefit is that the Federal government can employ the services of cybersecurity experts outside of the United States. Access to this new pool of experts could also be advantageous in that a new pool of personnel experts can present a different view of cybersecurity that is outside the culture of the US culture of cybersecurity professionals. Another major advantage is that the government can increase public/private sector partnerships that are critical for success in cybersecurity. The government can act as a liaison between the public and private sector to proactively monitor cybersecurity threats.

Drawbacks

The major drawbacks are related to accountability and the regulatory environment. The federal government will have very little accountability to monitor an online community that shares information about data mining. Some of the advantages discussed above also present some issues that are drawbacks. The Federal government will be challenged to exert control over a shared online community. Additionally, the Federal government must also implement a process where the information is verified. For example, if a patch for a network is recommended for a private organization, the Federal government may be held accountable if they recommend a patch from cybersecurity professional.

The regulatory environment will also be a drawback for government intervention in an online data mining community technology such as Sec Buzzers. The government will be compelled to implement a process to vet the information, and this process will slow the process of determining a remedy for the vulnerability. This will in effect negate the advantage of the speed of the remedy for the vulnerability. The Federal government will in all likely need to establish another law enforcement unit to monitor this partnership and community. This will require more training and expertise in an area that is currently lacking in cybersecurity enforcement.

Conclusion

Sec Buzzers, like all emergent technologies, is an evolving dynamic that may or may not have a significant impact on cybersecurity. Sec Buzzers may ultimately not prove to be successful. However, the concept (and need) of the sharing of information and expertise in a timely manner is a necessity in cybersecurity. The success or lack of success of Sec Buzzers will be very hard to determine in a precise manner. Perhaps the test of time will be the only measure of success. If Sec Buzzers continues to grow and evolve, it should be considered a success.

Sec Buzzers is an emergent technology that attempts to leverage the sheer enormity and openness of social networks, corral data mining techniques and leverage cybersecurity expertise in one application. Sec Buzzers seeks to identify a cluster of expertise that can more expediently identify a vulnerability and then publicly disseminate potential solutions. Sec Buzzers is currently doing these with very limited resources. At this moment, it appears that Sec Buzzers is staffed by volunteers, which has disadvantages and advantages. Sec Buzzers the technology concept, more so than the actual online learning community, will continue to evolve as data mining and the need for sharing cyber expertise becomes a necessity.

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